

Decision Frameworks Under Uncertainty with Soft Lattice Matrix

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Abstract— The investigation at hand is intended to define a Soft Lattice Matrix in soft set theory by using the characteristic function of relation. On these Soft Lattice Matrices, we have added a few new operations and we have covered all the foregoing definitions and operations with relevant examples. The applicability of Soft Lattice Matrices via Soft Lattice Topological Spaces is demonstrated through real-life decision-making scenarios involving multiple decision-makers. Various problems related to decision-making, particularly those arising in the context of applications for student jobs, are examined. The study considers the diverse preferences and considerations of multiple persons, such as Dad, Mom, and Staff, to propose a robust decision-making approach tailored to real-world challenges.

Keywords— Soft Lattice Set, Soft Lattice Matrix, Weighted Soft Lattice Matrix, Transpose of Soft Lattice Matrix, Product of Soft Lattice Matrix, Soft Lattice Topology.

MSC 2020 Classification— 97E60, 06B23, 54A05, 54A99

I. INTRODUCTION

A generic mathematical tool for handling vague, ambiguous, and poorly specified objects, soft set theory was initially presented by Molodtsov[8] in 1999. The smoothness of functions, game theory, operations research, Riemann integration, Perron integration, probability, theory of measurement, and other areas are only a few of the areas in which Molodtsov employed soft set theory with success. Maji et al.[7] conducted a thorough theoretical investigation on soft sets and provided an application of soft sets in a decision-making issue employing the rough sets. Soft lattice topological spaces (in short SLTS), which are declared over an SL 'L' with a given set of parameters A and are also a generalization of STS, were recently developed in 2021 by Sandhya S. Pai and T. Baiju [9]. Then, in 2023[1], we keep looking into an SL-interior, SL-exterior, and SL- border in the work extension of SL-sets which is essential for more study on soft lattice topology then the thoughts of soft lattice contra continuous mapping (on short SLCCM) in SLTS was also covered in-depth, along with the concepts of SL-contra open and SL-contra closed sets in the year 2024[5].

To understand soft sets, let's first define soft matrices[2-4] (in short SM). Many benefits come with this representation. Soft sets are represented by a minimum computer because matrices are simple to store and manipulate. Instead of utilizing rough sets and fuzzy soft sets, we also design a more practical soft lattice matrix decision-making model that can be effectively used in a wide range of uncertain scenarios. Also following the presumption of soft sets, soft lattices (on short SL) as a layout has emerged. F. Li [6] investigated, outlined and provided the fundamental principles of soft lattices. Additionally, E. Kuppuswamy used soft sets to lattices in 2011. As a supplement to what F. Li has done, This is the order in which the remainder of the paper is presented. We define soft lattice matrices (in short SLM) and how they work in the normal soft sets. Here SLM qualities are defined with the term's addition, product of soft lattice matrix, and by using the concept of choice matrix(in short CM) we made how to decide with more number of decision makers. We give an example to demonstrate the successful operation of these approaches.

To present readers with an engaging read on my topic, I include a simple counter-example below in the article. The conclusion drawn from the application of this decision-making model, incorporating the product of soft lattice matrix with weighted soft lattice matrix and soft lattice topological spaces, indicates

that it provides consistent and reliable results for selecting the optimal job option for the student. This conclusion may also suggest the broader applicability of the model to other decision problems with uncertainties. In summary, my approach involves integrating soft set theory into a soft lattice matrix decision-making model to address uncertainties in selecting the optimal job option for a student. The conclusion emphasizes the practicality and effectiveness of this approach, which can be extended to other similar decision problems.

II. OVERTURE

Definition:2.1[1] Let A be a group of parameters and U be a starting universe set. Let P be a non-void subset of A , and let $\wp(U)$ be the power set of U . When F is provided by $F: P \rightarrow \wp(U)$, then a pair (F_p, A) corresponds to a soft set over U . For $\rho \in A$, $F(\rho)$ may be considered as the set of ρ elements of the soft sets (F_p, A) . A soft set is not a set. The soft set is denoted by F_p .

Definition:2.2[5] A soft point in x_p is designated as a soft subset (F_p, A) of U , if for the element $\rho \in A$, $F(\rho) \neq \phi$ and $F(\rho') = \phi \forall \rho' \in A - \{\rho\}$.

Definition:2.3[2] Let (F_p, A) be a soft lattice over U , then a soft subset of UXA is uniquely defined by $R_A = \{(l, \rho) : \rho \in A, l \in F_A^L(\rho)\}$ which is called relation from (F_A^L, A) . Now the characteristic function of R_A is written by,

$$\delta R_A: UXA \rightarrow \{0, 1\}, \delta R_A(u, \rho) \begin{cases} 1, & (u, \rho) \in R_A \\ 0, & (u, \rho) \notin R_A \end{cases}$$

Definition:2.4[2] Let $U = \{u_1, u_2, u_3, \dots, u_m\}$, $A = \{\rho_1, \rho_2, \rho_3, \dots, \rho_n\}$ then the characteristic function of L_A can be represented by the tabular form,

TABLE I
CHARACTERISTIC FUNCTION

	ρ_1	ρ_2		ρ_n
u_1	$\delta R_A(u_1, \rho_1)$	$\delta R_A(u_1, \rho_2)$		$\delta R_A(u_1, \rho_n)$
u_2	$\delta R_A(u_2, \rho_1)$	$\delta R_A(u_2, \rho_2)$		$\delta R_A(u_2, \rho_n)$
.....				
u_m	$\delta R_A(u_m, \rho_1)$	$\delta R_A(u_m, \rho_2)$		$\delta R_A(u_m, \rho_n)$

If $s_{ij} = \delta R_A(u, \rho)$ we can define matrix $[s_{ij}]_{m \times n} = \begin{pmatrix} s_{11} & s_{12} & \dots & s_{1n} \\ s_{21} & s_{22} & \dots & s_{2n} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ s_{m1} & s_{m2} & \dots & s_{mn} \end{pmatrix}$ which corresponds to the $(F_p,$

$A)$ over L and is commonly referred to as a soft lattice matrix (in Short SLM) of order $m \times n$. The unique characteristic (F_p, A) is $[s_{ij}]_{m \times n}$. As a result, we will use these two notions interchangeably to identify any soft lattice sets (F_p, A) together with its soft lattice matrix (SLM).

Definition:2.5[2] The parameters are shown by the square matrix's rows and columns. If CM is a choice matrix, then its element $CM(i, j)$ is defined as follows:

$$CM(i, j) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{where the decision-makers choice parameters are the } i\text{th and } j\text{th parameters} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise, i.e., in the event when at least one of the } i\text{th and } j\text{th parameters is not selectable} \end{cases}$$

Depending on how many people are making decisions, there are several kinds of choice matrices.

Definition:2.6[9] A sub-lattice of a lattice L' is a non-void subset of L that is a lattice with the same meet and join operation as L, i.e., $\alpha, \beta \in L$ implies $\alpha \vee \beta, \alpha \wedge \beta \in L'$.

Definition:2.7[9] A Complete lattice L and X is the parameters of the soft lattice over L, the triplet $M = (F, X, L)$, $F: A \rightarrow \wp(L)$ is called soft lattice(in Short SL) if $F(\rho)$ is the sub-lattice of L for each $\rho \in A$. Then the soft lattice is represented by F_A^L .

Definition2.8[9] Assume that L represents any complete lattice and that A symbolizes a non-void set of parameters. Assuming that θ contains complete members, uniquely complemented soft lattice over L, then θ is soft lattice topology, the following conditions must hold:

- (i) $\phi_A, L_A \in \theta$.
- (ii) The union of any number of soft lattices in θ belongs to θ .
- (iii) the intersection of any two soft lattices in θ belongs to θ .

Then the triplet (L, θ, A) is called a soft lattice topological space (SL-space or SLTS) over L. The members of θ are called soft lattice-open sets in L. Also, a soft lattice (F_A^L) is called a soft lattice- closed if the relative complement $(F_A^L)^C$ belongs to θ .

III.SOFT LATTICE MATRIX

Definition:3.1 Let (F_A^L) be a soft lattice over L, then a soft lattice subset of LXA is uniquely defined by $R_{L_A} = \{(l, \rho): \rho \in A, l \in F_A^L(\rho)\}$ which is called relation from (F_A^L, A) . Now the characteristic function of R_{L_A} is written by,

$$\lambda_{R_{L_A}} : LXA \rightarrow \{0, 1\}, \lambda_{R_{L_A}}(l, \rho) \begin{cases} 1, (l, \rho) \in R_{L_A} \\ 0, (l, \rho) \notin R_{L_A} \end{cases}$$

Definition:3.2 Let $L = \{l_1, l_2, l_3, \dots, l_m\}$, $A = \{\rho_1, \rho_2, \rho_3, \dots, \rho_n\}$ then the characteristic function of L_A can be represented by the tabular form,

TABLE III
CHARACTERISTIC FUNCTION FOR SOFT LATTICE MATRIX

	ρ_1	ρ_1		ρ_1
l_1	$\lambda_{R_{L_A}}(l_1, \rho_1)$	$\lambda_{R_{L_A}}(l_1, \rho_2)$		$\lambda_{R_{L_A}}(l_1, \rho_n)$
l_2	$\lambda_{R_{L_A}}(l_2, \rho_1)$	$\lambda_{R_{L_A}}(l_2, \rho_2)$		$\lambda_{R_{L_A}}(l_2, \rho_n)$
.....				
l_m	$\lambda_{R_{L_A}}(l_m, \rho_1)$	$\lambda_{R_{L_A}}(l_m, \rho_2)$		$\lambda_{R_{L_A}}(l_m, \rho_n)$

If $l_{ij} = \lambda_{R_{L_A}}(l, \rho)$ we can define matrix $[l_{ij}]_{m \times n} = \begin{pmatrix} l_{11} & l_{12} & \dots & l_{1n} \\ l_{21} & l_{22} & \dots & l_{2n} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ l_{m1} & l_{m2} & \dots & l_{mn} \end{pmatrix}$ which corresponds to the

F_A^L over L and is commonly referred to as a soft lattice matrix (in Short SLM) of order $m \times n$. The unique characteristic (F_A^L) is $[l_{ij}]_{m \times n}$. As a result, we will use these two notions interchangeably to identify any soft lattice sets (F_A^L) together with its soft lattice matrix (SLM).

Example:3.3 Here we consider the soft lattice $L_A = \{l_1, l_2, l_3, l_4, l_5\}$ as universal set of bikes and $A = \{\rho_1, \rho_2, \rho_3, \rho_4, \rho_5\}$ be the set of parameters which is denoted as its features in bikes.

Figure 1 – Complete lattice

Here, the complete lattice is structured in the top quality of bikes. If $P = \{\rho_2, \rho_3, \rho_5\} \subset A$ and $F_A^L(\rho_2) = \{l_3, l_4, l_5\}$, $F_A^L(\rho_3) = \{l_2\}$, $F_A^L(\rho_5) = L_A$, Now put down the $F_A^L = \{(\rho_1, \phi), (\rho_2, \{l_3, l_4, l_5\}), (\rho_3, \{l_2\}), (\rho_4, \phi), (\rho_5, L_A)\}$ and then the relation form of F_A^L is inscribed by $F_A^L = \{(l_1, \rho_5), (l_2, \rho_3), (l_2, \rho_5), (l_3, \rho_2), (l_3, \rho_5), (l_4, \rho_2), (l_4, \rho_5), (l_5, \rho_2), (l_5, \rho_5)\}$. Accordingly, the SLM by $[l_{ij}] = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$.

Definition:3.4 Let $[l_{ij}]$ be an $m \times n$ soft lattice matrix. Then the complement soft lattice matrix of is denoted by $[l_{ij}]^c$ and is defined by $[l_{ij}]^c = [k_{ij}]$, where $[k_{ij}]$ is also an SLM of order $m \times n$ and $[k_{ij}] = 1 - (l_{ij}) \forall i, j$.

Definition:3.5 A weighted soft lattice matrix is an SLM that includes a non-negative integer as one of its elements. In this case, much like in a SLM, every row is related to a particular object, and every column is related to a particular parameter. The weight of the object analogous to every row is the total of all the components in that row. As a result, the weight of all objects relating to a null soft lattice matrix is zero weight. This is simply symbolized by WSLM.

Example:3.6 Make it possible for us the set of an initial universe $L_A = \{l_1, l_2, l_3, l_4, l_5, l_6\}$ be the set of best mobile phones in India i.e., Samsung Galaxy S25 Ultra 5G, Apple iPhone 14 ProMax, Vivo X90 pro, Xiaomi 13pro, Google pixel 7 pro 5G, Oppo Find N2 Flip and the set of parameters $A = \{\text{Snapdragon 8Gen 2, 5000mAh, 12 GB RAM, AMOLED, 32 MP Front Cam, 6.8 inch display}\} = \{\rho_1, \rho_2, \rho_3, \rho_4, \rho_5, \rho_6\}$.

Figure 2 – Complete lattice

Then, $[l_{ij}] = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$ be a WSLM related to the exact universe L_A . Here as the 1st row has the

highest weight, the object corresponding to the 1st row. i.e., 'l₁' mostly satisfies the parameters concerned.

Now the F_A^L corresponding to this WSLM denoting the best basic features in mobile phones (l_{ij}) is $(F_A^L) = \{(\rho_1, \{l_1, l_4\}), (\rho_2, \{l_1, l_5\}), (\rho_3, \{l_1, l_3, l_4, l_5\}), (\rho_4, \{l_1, l_3, l_4, l_6\}), (\rho_5, \{l_3, l_4, l_6\}), (\rho_6, \{l_1, l_6\})\}$.

Here the F_A^L be a complete lattice. The figure of the complete lattice is arranged in prices of mobile phones. The join($\vee$) and meet($\wedge$) of a set of mobiles denote the highest and lowest price of mobile phones.

Example:3.7 Let the set of initial universe $L_A = \{l_1, l_2, l_3, l_4, l_5\}$ be the set of shoes and the set of parameters $A = \{\rho_1, \rho_2, \rho_3, \rho_4, \rho_5, \rho_6, \rho_7\}$.

Figure 3 – Complete lattice

Then, $[l_{ij}] = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 1 & 2 & 0 & 0 & 2 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 3 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 2 & 3 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 3 & 0 \\ 4 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$ be a WSLM pertains to the identical universe L_A . Since the third row

has the most weight in this case, object l_3 , which relates to the third row, mostly meets the relevant characteristics. At this point, the F_A^L correlates to the WSLM representing Shoe models with rainbow colors [l_{ij}] is $(F_A^L) = \{(\rho_1, \{l_2, l_3, l_5\}), (\rho_2, \{l_1, l_5\}), (\rho_3, \{l_1, l_2, l_3, l_4\}), (\rho_4, \{l_1, l_3, l_5\}), (\rho_5, \{l_5\}), (\rho_6, \{l_2, l_3, l_4\}), (\rho_7, \{l_1, l_2, l_3\})\}$. With a special indication that the parameter ρ_1 , l_3 is three times and l_5 is four times better than l_2 . The parameter ρ_2 is satisfied by l_1, l_5 maintaining the same weight. Next l_1, l_2, l_3 , and l_4 of parameters ρ_4 equally maintain the weight. The parameter ρ_4 , l_1 is two times better than l_3 and l_5 . Furthermore, the parameter ρ_5 only satisfies the object l_5 . The parameter ρ_6 , l_4 is three times and l_3 is two times better than l_2 . Finally, l_3 is three times, and l_1 two times is better than l_2 in the parameter ρ_7 .

Here Complete lattice is arranged in demand of shoe models.

Definition:3.8 A SLM of order $m \times n$ is said to be a null SLM or zero SLM if every component is null. A null SLM is denoted by ϕ_M . Now the F_{1A}^L is associated with a null SLM must be a null F_A^L .

Definition:3.9 A SLM of order $m \times n$ is said to be a Complete or Absolute SLM if every component are same. A complete SLM is denoted by L_M . Now the F_{1A}^L is associated with an absolute SLM must be an absolute F_A^L .

Definition:3.10 The transpose of square soft lattice matrix [l_{ij}] of order $m \times n$ is another square SLM of order $m \times n$ obtained from [l_{ij}] by interchanging its row and columns. It is denoted by [l_{ij}]^T. Therefore the F_{1A}^L associated with [l_{ij}]^T becomes a new F_{1A}^L over the same universe and over the set of parameters.

Example:3.11 Consider from the Example:3.6, The complete lattice set of $(F_A^L) = \{(\text{Snapdragon 8 Gen 2, } \{l_1, l_4\}), (5000 \text{ mAh, } \{l_1, l_5\}), (12 \text{ GB RAM, } \{l_1, l_3, l_4, l_5\}), (\text{AMOLED, } \{l_1, l_3, l_4, l_6\}), (32\text{MP Front Cam, } \{l_3, l_4, l_6\}), (6.8 \text{ inch display, } \{l_1, l_6\})\}$. Whose associated SLM is, $[l_{ij}] = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$, Now, its

transpose of SLM, $[l_{ij}]^T = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$, Therefore the F_A^L associated with $[l_{ij}]^T$ is $(G_A^L) = \{(\text{Samsung Galaxy S25 Ultra 5G, } \{\rho_1, \rho_2, \rho_3, \rho_4, \rho_6\}), (\text{Vivo X90 pro, } \phi), (\text{Apple i-phone 14 Promax, } \{\rho_3, \rho_4, \rho_5\}), (\text{Xiaomi 13 pro, } \{\rho_1, \rho_3, \rho_4, \rho_5\}), (\text{Google Pixel 7pro 5G, } \{\rho_2, \rho_3\}), (\text{Oppo Find N2 Flip, } \{\rho_4, \rho_5, \rho_6\})\}$.

Definition:3.12 If F_{1A}^L and F_{2A}^L have the same order, then they are considered able to conform for addition. The SLM, whose elements are taken as the maximum of the appropriate components of two soft lattice matrices, F_{1A}^L and F_{2A}^L , of the same order, is the sum of the two soft lattice matrices, F_{1A}^L and F_{2A}^L . In light of this, the addition of two soft lattice matrices with order $m \times n$, l_{ij} and k_{ij} , is referred to as $l_{ij} \oplus k_{ij} = m_{ij}$ where m_{ij} is also $m \times n$ SLM and $m_{ij} = \max \{l_{ij}, k_{ij}\} \forall ij$.

Definition:3.13 Let A be the collection of parameters and L_A be the set of universes. Suppose that P be any SLM and Q be any choice matrix (CM) concerned with the same universe L_A and A. Now, SLM and CM are mentioned that they are flexible for the product $SLM \otimes CM$ if the number of columns of SLM equals the number of rows of the CM. Consequently, the product becomes a WSLM. $SLM \otimes CM$ or just $(SLM.CM)$ can be portrayed as the product.

If $SLM = (l_{ij})_{m \times n}$ and $CM = (k_{jk})_{n \times p}$, then $SLM \otimes CM = (m_{ik})_{m \times p}$, Where $m_{ik} = \sum_{j=1}^n \min\{(l_{ij}), (k_{jk})\}$.

Example:3.14 Let L_A be the set of four movies given by $L = \{l_1, l_2, l_3, l_4\}$. Here the set of parameters assigned by $A = \{\text{Action, Adventures, Comedy, Horror}\} = \{\rho_1, \rho_2, \rho_3, \rho_4\}$ which describes the genre of movies. Suppose that the choice parameters of Friend 1 are $P = \{\rho_1, \rho_4\}$. Now according to the choice parameters of friend 1, we have the F_A^L denoting the favorite movie genre of friend 1, Here the Complete lattice is laid out based upon the rating of movies.

Figure 4 – Complete lattice

$(F_A^L) = \{(\rho_1, \{l_2, l_3, l_4\}), (\rho_2, \phi), (\rho_3, \phi), (\rho_4, \{l_1, l_4\})\}$, and the SLM of the (F_A^L) be $[l_{ij}] = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$. Again, the choice matrix of friend 1 is, $CM = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$ Since the number of columns of the

soft lattice $[l_{ij}]$ is equal to the number of rows of the choice matrix SM_C , they are conformable for the

product. Therefore, $\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \otimes \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 2 & 0 & 0 & 2 \end{pmatrix}$ according to multiplication rule. Here, the

parameter l_4 is the highest WSLM and we decide the favorite movie of Friend 1.

Example:3.15 Here, the problem is two doctors are from reputed hospitals, then they are consulting their breast cancer patients categorized by stages. Now we find out which treatments are going on the hospitals conclude by stages. Let L be the set of six standard treatments i.e., $L_A = \{\text{Surgery, Radiotherapy, Hormonal therapy, Chemotherapy, HER2 Targeted therapy, Immunotherapy}\} = \{l_1, l_2, l_3, l_4, l_5, l_6\}$, Let A be the set of parameters given by $A = \{\text{Stage 0, Stage 1, Stage 2, Stage 3, Stage 4}\} = \{\rho_1, \rho_2, \rho_3, \rho_4, \rho_5\}$. Now let the (F_A^L) denoting "treatment taking by consulting stages" is given by $(F_A^L) = \{\text{Stage 0}=\{l_1, l_2, l_3\}, \text{Stage 1}=\{l_1, l_2, l_4, l_5\}, \text{Stage 2}=\{l_1, l_2, l_3, l_4, l_5\}, \text{Stage 3}=\{l_1, l_2, l_3, l_4, l_5\}, \text{Stage 4}=\{l_3, l_4, l_5, l_6\}\}$.

Presume that, the choice parameter set of doctor (x) be, $P = \{\rho_2, \rho_3, \rho_4\} \subseteq A$ and the set of choice parameters of Doctor(y) be, $Q = \{\rho_3\} \subseteq A$. Let's now proceed based on the choice of parameters. Of Doctor(x) and Doctor(y), We have the (F_A^L) which describes" treatment taking by consulting stages" and

the SLM of the (F_A^L) are, $[x_{ij}] = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}; [y_{ij}] = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$.

Now the combined choice matrix of Doctor(x)and Doctor(y) is, $\rho_B \begin{pmatrix} \rho_A \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$ then its transpose

of the combined matrix is, $\rho_A \begin{pmatrix} \rho_B \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$ corresponding product SLM are,

$$L_A \begin{pmatrix} \rho_A \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \otimes \rho_A \begin{pmatrix} \rho_B \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 3 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 3 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 3 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 3 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} :$$

$$L_B \begin{pmatrix} \rho_B \\ 00100 \\ 00100 \\ 00100 \\ 00100 \\ 00100 \\ 00000 \end{pmatrix} \otimes \rho_B \begin{pmatrix} \rho_A \\ 00000 \\ 00000 \\ 01110 \\ 00000 \\ 00000 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 01110 \\ 01110 \\ 01110 \\ 01110 \\ 01110 \\ 01110 \\ 00000 \end{pmatrix}.$$

The sum of these product SLM is,

$$\begin{pmatrix} 00300 \\ 00300 \\ 00200 \\ 00300 \\ 00300 \\ 00000 \end{pmatrix} \oplus \begin{pmatrix} 01110 \\ 01110 \\ 01110 \\ 01110 \\ 01110 \\ 00000 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 01410 \\ 01410 \\ 01310 \\ 01410 \\ 01410 \\ 00000 \end{pmatrix}$$

The SLM's first, second, fourth, and fifth-row results now have the most weight. Treatments $l_1, l_2, l_4,$ and l_5 are weighted more than treatment l_3 . Based on this, we can conclude that, in this hospital, patients receive treatment $l_1, l_2, l_4,$ and l_5 frequently. Treatment l_3 is also taken by patients there, but it is slightly less weighted than other treatments, so that's why the doctor is concerned about expanding the facility of treatment l_3 . Therapy l_6 is thus not being provided at this hospital as the patient receiving it is not there. As a result, the doctor is concerned about the stage at which patients are classified for therapy l_6 .

IV. APPLICATION PROBLEMS

In this decision-making model, we separately find the results by the product of soft lattice matrix with weighted soft lattice matrix and soft lattice topological spaces, it is concluded that both results obtained are consistent and dependable when determining the best career option for the student.

Example:4.1 Here, our problem is to find which country and jobs are suitable for a student. The parents of a student discuss their choices with one of her professors. Suppose that L be the set of top 5 working countries i.e., $L_A = \{USA, Canada, Japan, UK, India\} = \{l_1, l_2, l_3, l_4, l_5\}$, and set of parameters shown by $A = \{\text{Web developer, Java developer, Security Analyst in IT, Software Engineer, HTML/CSS writer}\} = \{\rho_1, \rho_2, \rho_3, \rho_4, \rho_5\}$. Now let the (F_A^L) denoting "jobs in different countries" is given by $(F_A^L) = \{\text{Web developer}=\{l_2, l_5\}, \text{Java developer}=\{l_4\}, \text{Security Analyst in IT} =\{l_3, l_5\}, \text{Software Engineer}=\{l_1, l_2, l_5\}, \text{HTML/CSS writer}=\{l_1\}\}$.

Figure 5 – Complete lattice

The SLM is structured here according to the top placement of countries.

Allow the collection of, choice parameter of Dad(x) be, $K = \{\rho_2, \rho_3, \rho_4\} \subseteq A$ and choice parameter of Mom(y) be, $R = \{\rho_2, \rho_4, \rho_5\} \subseteq A$. Let us now proceed under the choice parameters of Dad and Mom, We have the (F_A^L) which describes "jobs in different countries" and the SLM of the dad and mom are $[x_{ij}]$

$$= \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}; [y_{ij}] = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}. \text{ Suppose Dad decide a country based on his choice of parameters } K =$$

$$\{\rho_2, \rho_3, \rho_4\} \subseteq A \text{ Now the choice matrix of Dad is } CM_x = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \text{ In same way Dad and Mom decide}$$

a country together based on their choice of parameters $R = \{\rho_2, \rho_4, \rho_5\} \subseteq A$, Thereafter, the combined

$$SM_C \text{ of Dad and Mom is } CM_{(x,y)} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Now the combined CM is associated with the third decision-maker of one of the student staff(z). Then, the Staff is willing to decide on a country together with Mom and Dad's decision based on his choice parameters of job security in IT and HTML/CSS Writer that was created a subset C of the parameter set E. Therefore, $I = \{\rho_3, \rho_5\} \subseteq A$. Let the associated SLM, of H_A^L of staff(z), $[z_{ij}] =$

$$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}. \text{ Following that, the combined SMC of Dad(x), Mom(y) and a Staff(z) will be three different}$$

types which are

$$a) CM_{(z, x \wedge y)} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} [\because \text{ the set of common choice parameter of Dad(x) and Mom(y) is } K \wedge$$

$$R = \{\rho_2, \rho_4\}]$$

[The entries here $\rho_{ij} = 1$ suggest that ρ_i is a choice parameter of Staff and ρ_j is a common choice parameter of Dad(X) and Mom(y). Now $\rho_{ij} = 0$ signifies either that ρ_i lacks a choice parameter of Staff or ρ_j does not exist as a common choice parameter of Dad(x) and Mom(y).]

$$b) CM_{(x, y \wedge z)} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} [\because \text{ the set of common choice parameter of Mom(y) and Staff(z) is } R \wedge$$

$$I = \{\rho_5\}]$$

$$c) CM_{(y, x \wedge z)} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} [\because \text{ the set of common choice parameter of Dad(x) and Staff(z) is } K \wedge I$$

$= \{\rho_3\}]$. Corresponding Products of soft lattice matrices are,

$$\begin{aligned}
 &L_K \begin{pmatrix} \rho_K \\ 00010 \\ 00010 \\ 00100 \\ 01000 \\ 00110 \end{pmatrix} \otimes \rho_K \begin{pmatrix} \rho_{RAI} \\ 00000 \\ 00001 \\ 00001 \\ 00001 \\ 00000 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 00001 \\ 00001 \\ 00001 \\ 00001 \\ 00002 \end{pmatrix} \\
 &L_R \begin{pmatrix} \rho_R \\ 00011 \\ 00010 \\ 00000 \\ 01000 \\ 00010 \end{pmatrix} \otimes \rho_R \begin{pmatrix} \rho_{KAI} \\ 00000 \\ 00100 \\ 00000 \\ 00100 \\ 00100 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 00200 \\ 00100 \\ 00000 \\ 00100 \\ 00100 \end{pmatrix} \\
 &L_I \begin{pmatrix} \rho_I \\ 00001 \\ 00000 \\ 00100 \\ 00000 \\ 00100 \end{pmatrix} \otimes \rho_I \begin{pmatrix} \rho_{KAR} \\ 00000 \\ 00000 \\ 01010 \\ 00000 \\ 01010 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 01010 \\ 00000 \\ 01010 \\ 00000 \\ 01010 \end{pmatrix}, \text{ The sum of these product soft Lattice matrices} \\
 &\text{is, } \begin{pmatrix} 00001 \\ 00001 \\ 00001 \\ 00001 \\ 00002 \end{pmatrix} \oplus \begin{pmatrix} 00200 \\ 00100 \\ 00000 \\ 00100 \\ 00100 \end{pmatrix} \oplus \begin{pmatrix} 01010 \\ 00000 \\ 01010 \\ 00000 \\ 01010 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 01211 \\ 00101 \\ 01011 \\ 00101 \\ 01112 \end{pmatrix}. \text{ The first and last rows of the resultant}
 \end{aligned}$$

SLM have the highest weight. Therefore, l_1 and l_5 are the optimal choice objects. So, Dad, Mom, and Staff finally decided on a country USA and India.

Example:4.2 We take the following case as an above example, It is possible to analyze the top 5 working country's occupations using soft lattice topological spaces. The student's father, mother, and staff choose a working country by using some of the finest occupations of the parameters $A = \{\rho_1, \rho_2, \rho_3, \rho_4, \rho_5\}$. The top 5 working countries are denoted by $L_A = \{l_1, l_2, l_3, l_4, l_5\}$. Determining the right criterion for a student to take her working nation and career into consideration is the challenge.

$$\begin{aligned}
 (F_A^L) &= \{(\rho_2, \{l_4\}), (\rho_3, \{l_3, l_5\}), (\rho_4, \{l_1, l_2, l_5\})\} \\
 (G_A^L) &= \{(\rho_2, \{l_4\}), (\rho_4, \{l_1, l_2, l_5\}), (\rho_5, \{l_1\})\} \\
 (H_A^L) &= \{(\rho_3, \{l_3, l_5\}), \rho_5, (\{l_1\})\}
 \end{aligned}$$

Then $\theta = \{\phi_M, F_A^L, G_A^L, H_A^L, F_A^L \cup G_A^L, F_A^L \cup H_A^L, G_A^L \cup H_A^L, F_A^L \cap G_A^L, F_A^L \cap H_A^L, G_A^L \cap H_A^L, (F_A^L \cup G_A^L \cup H_A^L), (F_A^L \cap G_A^L \cap H_A^L)\}$, L_M is a soft lattice topology over L_A where $E = \{\rho_1, \rho_2, \rho_3, \rho_4, \rho_5\}$.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Psi_{l_0} = \text{matrix } (\phi_M) & \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} & \Psi_{l_1} = \text{matrix } (L_M) & \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \\
 \Psi_{l_2} = \text{matrix } (F_A^L) & \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} & \Psi_{l_3} = \text{matrix } (G_A^L) & \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\Psi_{1_4} = \text{matrix } (H_A^L) = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\begin{aligned} F_A^L \cap G_A^L &= \{(\rho_2, \{l_4\}), (\rho_4, \{l_1, l_2, l_5\})\} \\ G_A^L \cap H_A^L &= \{(\rho_5, \{l_1\})\} \\ F_A^L \cap H_A^L &= \{(\rho_3, \{l_3, l_5\})\} \\ F_A^L \cup G_A^L &= \{(\rho_2, \{l_4\}), (\rho_3, \{l_3, l_5\}), (\rho_4, \{l_1, l_2, l_5\}), (\rho_5, \{l_1\})\} \\ G_A^L \cup H_A^L &= \{(\rho_2, \{l_4\}), (\rho_3, \{l_3, l_5\}), (\rho_4, \{l_1, l_2, l_5\}), (\rho_5, \{l_1\})\} \\ F_A^L \cup H_A^L &= \{(\rho_2, \{l_4\}), (\rho_3, \{l_3, l_5\}), (\rho_4, \{l_1, l_2, l_5\}), (\rho_5, \{l_1\})\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\Psi_{1_5} = \text{matrix } (F_A^L \cap G_A^L) = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad \Psi_{1_6} = \text{matrix } (G_A^L \cap H_A^L) = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\Psi_{1_7} = \text{matrix } (F_A^L \cap H_A^L) = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad \Psi_{1_8} = \text{matrix } (F_A^L \cup G_A^L) = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\Psi_{1_9} = \text{matrix } (F_A^L \cup H_A^L) = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad \Psi_{1_{10}} = \text{matrix } (F_A^L \cup G_A^L) = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\begin{aligned} (F_A^L \cap G_A^L \cap H_A^L) &= \{ \phi_A \} \\ (F_A^L \cup G_A^L \cup H_A^L) &= \{(\rho_2, \{l_4\}), (\rho_3, \{l_3, l_5\}), (\rho_4, \{l_1, l_2, l_5\}), (\rho_5, \{l_1\})\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\Psi_{1_{11}} = \text{matrix } (F_A^L \cap G_A^L \cap H_A^L) = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\Psi_{1_{12}} = \text{matrix } (F_A^L \cup G_A^L \cup H_A^L) = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

Then, matrix $(\theta_A) = \{\Psi_{1_0}, \Psi_{1_1}, \Psi_{1_2}, \Psi_{1_3}, \Psi_{1_4}, \Psi_{1_5}, \Psi_{1_6}, \Psi_{1_7}, \Psi_{1_8}, \Psi_{1_9}, \Psi_{1_{10}}, \Psi_{1_{11}}, \Psi_{1_{12}}\}$

The choice of (F_A^L) , discussed by a dad, Mom, and her Staff depends on their own choices. The Dad, Mom, and Staff have to choose their parameter and individuality for the best jobs. Then we consider, the weighted soft lattice matrix which is possessed by the rule of union and the intersection of all parameters (i.e., $(F_A^L \cap G_A^L \cap H_A^L)$ and $(F_A^L \cup G_A^L \cup H_A^L)$). Therefore l_1 and l_5 are the optimal choice objects. Because Dad, Mom, and her staff made different choices, the intersection of the parameters, in this case,

results in the null matrix. So, we are unable to compose any conclusions. It is necessary to choose the outcome if the matrix is non-void.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Several types of soft lattice matrices have been described and various operations on them are demonstrated in the present research. Another benefit is that we have put up the idea of a choice matrix, which symbolizes the decision-maker's choice parameters. Lastly, we developed an approach to solve F_A^L based on decision-making issues utilizing these CM and recently described operations of soft lattice matrices. This novel method's unique feature is its ability to quickly and simply answer any soft lattice set-based decision-making problem with a large number of decision-makers using a straightforward computational process.

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